

REBOOT
EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

Final Report on Ethics

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT
Grant Agreement: 101094796 - HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01
Authors: Katharine Sarikakis, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou (UNIVIE)
Reviewers: Simon Haslauer (UNIVIE), Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE)

Object D8.4 Final Report on Ethics

WP WP8 (University of Vienna)

Deliverable Lead UNIVIE

Type R=report

Dissemination Level PU=public

Version 1.0

Funded by the
European Union

Metadata

Project	Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT
Acronym	REBOOT
Programme	Horizon Europe
Call	HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01
Grant Agreement No.	101094796
Project coordinator	Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE)
Licensing terms	CC-BY 4.0
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18268179
Authors	Angeliki Chatziefraimidou, Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE)
Reviewers	Simon Haslauer (UNIVIE), Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE)
Title	Final Report on Ethics
Deliverable No.	D8.4
WP No.	WP8
Deliverable Lead	UNIVIE
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Version	1.0
Description	Reporting on the ethical guidelines applied throughout the research process and tasks of the REBOOT project.
Keywords	Ethical consideration, ethical guidelines, ethical research
Language	English

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

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THE REBOOT PROJECT SUMMARY

This project aims to connect existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses, and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, firstly, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of measuring, analysing and evaluating the impact of policies and strategic pathways. Secondly, the project aspires to actively prepare for future audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only "what is" but also "what has been" and "what will be" from fresh perspectives.

REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action to optimise the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the European Union (EU) in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VoD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

1. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS IN REBOOT

In the REBOOT project, research activities have involved research subjects in both scholarly and dissemination activities, such as interviews, focus groups, surveys and workshops. During the conduction of such activities, the consortium has followed specific ethical principles both in interaction with research subjects and in the management of their personal data. In this report, the consortium presents the ethical requirements and principles followed throughout the research process. These ethical guidelines are used in combination with the Data Management Plan (Deliverables D1.2, D1.3 and D1.4). Additionally, the research project followed the institutions' procedures on conducting scientific research with human beings as described in the D8.1 (Consent forms for interviews and focus groups), D8.2 (Consortium ethics survey checklist) and D8.4 (Approved ethics requirements plan) submitted reports. Ethical requirements provide specific guidance across all relevant research tasks.

Important notice:

This document is to be understood as in synergy with the legal requirements of the protection of human rights, codes of conduct in research, as well as data management where applicable and as such the project's Data Management Plan is also to be consulted; it is not to be seen as an exclusive or exhaustive document but rather as one of summarising the fundamental ethical standards aspired and followed at the REBOOT project. Any unforeseen ethical issues emerging through the research or analysis process has been raised with the ethics mentors and where appropriate with the consortium.

Consortium Ethics Survey Checklist¹:

- The consortium understands research ethics as a matter of continuous process before, during and after the research process.
- The consortium considers research ethics as a living process in cooperation with human subjects, both in the roles of researchers and research participants.
- The epistemological ethical dimensions of the consortium's commitments are:
 - to listen to human subjects with respect, without judgement or sense of superiority;
 - to pay special attention to human subjects in particular whenever children (minors) are involved; the consortium pays particular attention to the commitment of "doing research with children" instead of "on children";

¹ Presented in the Deliverable D8.5.

- to pay special attention to human subjects especially in terms of historical marginalisations;
- to “give back” to respondents by way of information, briefing, advocacy;
- to involve subjects in the design of the research as equals with specific knowledges;
- to situate the researcher’s own background, beliefs and experiences within the process, acknowledge it and account for it and to be aware of matters of positionality and hierarchies throughout the process.

2. STATEMENTS OF CONDUCTING ETHICAL RESEARCH

The project fully complies with the European Code of Conduct. This applies also to research conducted to countries outside the European Union (EU), such as Türkiye, South Africa and countries in Latin America.

The research tasks are approved by Universities’ Ethics Committees.

The research conducted throughout the project entails the minimum risk for participants, adhering to the principle of not to harm the research participants in any way.

The research process of specific tasks and work packages was defined through regular consortium meetings, taking decisions in a common ground, developing research tools and agreeing on ethical procedures.

Compliance with ethical guidelines is integrated into every research task and is monitored by the two ethics’ mentors: the project coordinator Prof. Katharine Sarikakis and Prof. Caterina Sganga, stated in the Consortium Agreement (Point 6.1-General Structure). The mentors overviewed and consulted the consortium on ethical issues. For major ethical issues the Project Officer was informed.

Ethics in this research project extend to equality and diversity among the research participants.

The researchers are dedicated to accountability towards society as ethical responsibility. The consortium approaches the produced knowledge from institutions as one with the aim of serving the public. Therefore, no research aims at or allows for any human rights’ violation.

The consortium aspires to the principle of building knowledge based on previous work, including academic archives. At the same time, the produced research is available to the public, including current and future stakeholders, academics and policy makers, through open access publications, workshops and conferences.

The researchers are committed to represent participants' statements with accuracy, protecting participants' identity through anonymity.

3. SPECIFIC ETHICAL GUIDELINES FOLLOWED THROUGHOUT THE RESEARCH PROJECT

The participating universities and research institutions are the contracting authorities, that is, the parties responsible for data processing as defined by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Data collection relevant for the project's research commences only after obtaining voluntary written informed consent from all research participants, which entails an information sheet and an informed consent form. The participants were explicitly informed regarding their personal data collection, storage and safety procedures, as well as use of the collected data in the context of the research project. More specifically:

All participants declared that they understand that their consent to the collection, processing and usage of their personal data is freely given and can be revoked without any negative consequences.

Name and personal contact data have been stored separately from interview data, online questionnaire data and experimental studies data, inaccessible to third parties, and have only been used for internal organisation and contact purposes and queries as well as for research purposes.

Researchers' full professional contact details, including addresses and names were provided to participants for any questions and information.

The participating universities and research institutions have processed the following categories of personal data in the course of the current data processing: Name, electronic contact data, gender, age, residence region (country/state).

Legal basis for processing: The data has been processed on the basis of participants' consent for the purpose of carrying out the REBOOT research project. The legal basis for this is in particular the GDPR, namely Art. 6 Abs 1 lit a GDPR² (consent from the person concerned) as well as Art 9 Abs 2 lit j GDPR³ (research purposes in the public interest) in connection with the national Research Organisation Acts.

Participants' personal contact data (name, e-mail address) will be stored for up to one year after the end of the project and then deleted⁴. The audio data of interviews as well as any online questionnaires and experimental studies data will be stored for 10 years from the date of publication of the results of the project to demonstrate compliance with good scientific practice and will be deleted thereafter. The data required for the assertion, exercise and defence of legal claims are stored for up to 30 years and subsequently deleted.

Participants' data has not been forwarded to recipients outside the participating universities and research institutions.

All research participants, as people affected by data processing, have been provided the right to the following services from the participating universities and research institutions concerning their data: Information, correction, deletion, restriction, data transferability, termination of further processing, if the legal basis for processing is a prevailing legitimate interest on the part of the contracting authority or the data is processed for scientific or historical research purposes or for statistical uses.

Participants had the opportunity to lodge a complaint with the national data protection authorities in accordance with legal provisions, at any time, (especially Art. 15 to 22 GDPR with restrictions in § 2d Abs 6 FOG) concerning any data processing that was, in their opinion, not authorised.

Research data were selected for the purposes of research, publication, citation and publication on the (project) website and (project) social media (LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter).

² General Data Protection Regulation. (n.d.). *Article 6 — Lawfulness of processing*. In *GDPR-Info.eu*. Retrieved January 16, 2026, from <https://gdpr-info.eu/art-6-gdpr/>

³ General Data Protection Regulation. (n.d.). *Chapter 9 — Remedies, liability and penalties*. In *GDPR-Info.eu*. Retrieved January 16, 2026, from <https://gdpr-info.eu/chapter-9/>

⁴ In the case of Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR), participants' personal contact data (name, e-mail address) will be stored for up to ten years after the end of the project and then deleted.

In some cases, artificial intelligence was used as part of tools for transcribing interviews or translating anonymised transcripts from the local language into English. No personal data of research participants was entered or processed through artificial intelligence-assisted tools whatsoever.

Participants had the opportunity to withdraw consent given for data processing at any time without providing reasons or facing any consequences.

The collected data was fully anonymised without enabling any identification of the participants.

The sample of the quantitative data collected through surveys aimed to represent various socio-economic and geographic backgrounds.

Participants consented to be recorded during interviews and focus groups.

Participants provide their informed consent regarding photographs and interviews' content, stating that they can be used for research purposes and dissemination of the project.

Participants received all relevant information regarding the projects' objectives and the collaborating partners. They were encouraged to get clarifications for any questions and received the researchers' professional contact information for any questions arising after the data collection

4. THE CONSORTIUM RESPONDED TO ALL MEASURES INVOLVED TO ETHICAL RESEARCH

Participants did not get harmed in any way.

Researchers aimed to reduce and even diminish power dynamics between researchers and participants.

Researchers engaged with participants as equals, communicating at eye level, including minors.

In every stage of the research process, and especially in findings' interpretation, researchers took under consideration their own positionalities.

Participants in the whole research project were treated and perceived as research subjects with agency and not as research objects.

Participants had the option to receive the findings of the research they were involved in and generally the research aimed to “give back” to respondents through information exchange.

5. RESEARCH WITH MINORS

International best practices and recommendations were applied to ensure the highest level of protection of minor research participants, ensuring the respect and protection of their rights.

The information sheet was developed in a child-friendly language to be comprehensible for the target group.

The focus groups were conducted with small groups of five to eight children. Children were selected to be with their classmates to create a comfortable environment, which would convey communication among peers.

All communication of the research project, its aim and the research process was written in child-friendly language.

Along with the university’s Ethics Committees, approval was obtained from each Ministry of Education, where necessary, from the school boards and school principals and from children’s parents or legal guardians.

Additionally to written consent by legal guardians, participating minors provided their own oral informed assent before the commencement of data collection, confirming their present-day, voluntary participation.

Participants were aware of their right to withdraw at any time, without facing any negative consequences.

An aim of the study was to give voice to children and responsibly convey this to the public, other stakeholders and policy makers.

The researchers aimed to reduce hierarchical relations between researchers and participants, as well as adults and children.

During the data analysis, all participants’ data was fully anonymised and the researchers were aware of their responsibility to translate children’s voices to the public.

The researchers aspired to conduct research with children and not on children, recognising minors as research subjects, who co-create the research process.

Children did not get photographed during the research process and if so, they could not be in any way identified.

Children's personal information was completely anonymised without enabling any identification.

Children received small compensatory gifts such as pens, pencils, refreshments, snacks or cinema tickets after consultation with the school.

6. CONSERVATION OF THE CREATIVE PROCESS

An additional type of data refers to the conservation of the creative process regarding the film music which includes:

- screen copies
- music composition software programmes
- exchanges
- correspondence

Among them there are private data, which is not publicly accessible.

Original musical scores are part of the collected data.

A copyright contract was made by the Université Côte d'Azur (UCA) to secure the right of diffusion.

The recording sessions were filmed and the produced materials have been stored on UCA servers in the form of videos.

Disclaimer

This document is part of the outputs of the *Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT* project, which received funding from the Horizon Europe programme of the European Union under the Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

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Citation

Please cite this report as follows:

Sarikakis, K., & Chatziefrimidou, A. (2026). *Final Report on Ethics*. The REBOOT project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18268179>

Contact

Website: www.thereboot-project.eu

Email: reboot.2023@univie.ac.at

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REBOOT Contributors

UNIVERSIDAD
COMPLUTENSE
MADRID

KADİR HAS
ÜNİVERSİTESİ

Erasmus
University
Rotterdam

UNIVERSITEIT
GENT

uc3m

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Instituto Universitario del Cine Español

Sant'Anna
School of Advanced Studies - Pisa

UNIVERSITÉ
CÔTE D'AZUR

JYVÄSKYLÄN YLIOPISTO
UNIVERSITY OF JYVÄSKYLÄ

UNIVERSITY
OF WARSAW

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

